

GREENGAGE

ENGAGING CITIZENS - MOBILIZING TECHNOLOGY - DELIVERING GREEN DEAL

Data Management Plan 2

Work Package 1, Deliverable D1.12

AWAITING VALIDATION BY THE EUROPEAN COMMISSION

Data Management Plan 2

Work package 1, Deliverable D1.12

Please refer to this report as follows:

Javed, B., Khan, Z., Padiya, T. et al. (2025). Data Management Plan 2. Deliverable D1.12 of the Horizon Europe project GREENGAGE.

Project information	
Project name:	REENGAGE – Innovative governance, environmental observations and digital solutions in support of the Green Deal
Grant Agreement No.	101086530
Start date:	01/01/2023
Duration:	36 months
Coordinator:	AIT Austrian Institute of Technology Giefinggasse 4, 1210 Vienna, Austria
Contact:	Jan Peters-Anders, Research Engineer
	Funded by the European Union GA n° 101086530.
Deliverable details	
Description:	This document provides the Data Management Plan and procedures for the GREENGAGE project
Version:	Final
Dissemination level:	PU (Public)
Due date:	30/06/2025
Submission:	01/07/2025
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List of Acronyms

AIT	Austrian Institute of Technology
BCC	Bristol City Council
Borghi	I Borghi piu Belli D'Italia
BUAS	Breda University of Applied Sciences
CC	Creative Commons
CE	Collaborative Environment
CO	Citizen Observatory
DMP	Data Management Plan
DPIA	Data Protection Impact Assessment
DPO	Data Protection Officer
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GEOSS	Global Earth Observation System of Systems
GPS	Global Positioning System
FAIR	Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability and Reusability
KWMC	Knowles West Media Centre
POI	Point of Interest
PST	Pilot Support Team
UWE	University of the West of England Bristol

Glossary

Citizen Observatory	According to European project WeObserve, "Citizen Observatories (COs) are community-based environmental monitoring and information systems, that invite individuals to share observations, typically via mobile phone or the web. Throughout these activities citizens become able to participate in environmental management/local governance." [Reference: D2.1 - GREENGAGE Methodological Framework]
Open Science	In accordance with the EC's definition, the partners understand Open Science as "an approach based on open cooperative work and systematic sharing of knowledge and tools as early and widely as possible in the process". Specifically, GREENGAGE commits to all mandatory open science practices for all beneficiaries per grant agreement (Horizon Europe, Programme Guide, p.38).
GREEN Engine	A dedicated instance of the ESA's Urban-TEP (Thematic Exploitation Platform) platform leveraging GREEN Infrastructure to enable GREENGAGE CO activities

Executive summary

This document presents the second version of GREENGAGE's Data Management Plan (DMP). GREENGAGE's Data Management Plan was defined early and was updated throughout the lifetime of the project. The first version was initially created in June 2023 (Month 6) and then a revision was submitted in November 2024 (Month 23). The revised version elaborated GREENGAGE data sources, GREENGAGE project specific datasets, roles and responsibilities (controllers/joint controllers, processors, and data consumers) were clearly identified at this stage of the project, clear articulation of data categories and their collection methods and organisation, data security, accessibility, usage and processing, preservation, archiving, and disposal, and ethical considerations. The revised version also outlined the FAIR principles and how GREENGAGE is meant to implement them. This document builds up on the revised first version; as the revised version was submitted in Month 23, the second version is updated with any changes since Month 23. Mainly the FAIR principles, licencing information and examples of published resources are updated. This document is a guide for all GREENGAGE partners and external stakeholders who intend to use GREENGAGE data.

This is the final update of the data management plan. During this period assessment and application of FAIR principles in the project is completed. The license details presented in Section 7 (Table 1) are updated. Here we reflect on FAIR principles and lessons learned and make recommendations. This deliverable complements D6.3 Privacy Impact Assessment.

Related documents

- Deliverable D1.9 - Ethical Management and Activities Plan 1
- Deliverable D1.10 - Ethical Management and Activities Plan 2
- Deliverable D2.1 - GREENGAGE CO Methodological Framework
- Deliverable D2.2 - Use Cases and Requirements Analysis 1
- Deliverable D2.3 - Use Cases and Requirements Analysis 2
- Deliverable D2.4 - Smart Governance Models 1
- Deliverable D2.5 - Smart Governance Models 2
- Deliverable D2.6 - GREENGAGE Technological Requirements 1
- Deliverable D2.7 - GREENGAGE Technological Requirements 2
- Deliverable D4.1 - GREEN Engine and Manual 1
- Deliverable D4.2 - GREEN Engine and Manual 2
- Deliverable D6.3 - Privacy Impact Assessment

1 GREENGAGE summary

The pan-European Innovation Action, funded under the Horizon Europe Framework Programme, aims to promote innovative governance processes, and help public authorities in shaping their climate mitigation and adaptation policies. To achieve this aim, the GREENGAGE project will leverage citizens' participation and equip them with innovative digital solutions that will transform citizen's engagement and cities' effectiveness in delivering the European Green Deal objectives for carbon neutral cities.

Focusing on mobility, air quality and healthy living, citizens will be inspired to observe and co-create their cities by sensing their urban environments. The aim is to complement, validate, and enrich information in authoritative data held by the public administrations and public agencies. This will be facilitated by engaging with citizens to co-create green initiatives and to develop Citizen Observatories (CO). In GREENGAGE, Citizen Observatories will be a place where pilot cities will co-examine environmental issues integrating novel bottom-up process with top-down perspectives. This will provide the basis to co-create and co-design innovative solutions to monitor environmental problems at ground level with the help of citizens.

With two interrelated project dimensions, the project aims to enhance intelligence applied to city decision-making processes and governance by engaging with citizen observations integrated with Copernicus, Global Earth Observation System of Systems GEOSS, in-situ, and socio-economic intelligence, and by delivering innovative governance models based on novel toolboxes of decision-making methodologies and technologies.

The envisioned Citizen Observatory campaigns will be deployed and fully demonstrated in 5 pilot engagements in selected European cities and regions including: Bristol (the United Kingdom), Copenhagen (Denmark), Turano and Gerace (Italy) and the region of North Brabant (the Netherlands). These innovation pilots aim to highlight the need for smart city governance by promoting citizen engagement, co-creation, as well as gathering new data which will complement existing datasets and evidence-based decision and policymaking.

Figure 1: Structure of project GREENGAGE.

2 Introduction

The GREENGAGE project aims to promote innovative governance grounded on collaborative evidence-based decision-making, where citizens are actively involved in governance structure to co-create green initiatives to accelerate sustainable development, and to develop Citizen Observatories (CO); which also support the delivery of European Green Deal¹. Citizens will be facilitated to observe and co-create their cities by sensing their urban environments that will complement, validate, and enrich information held by public administration and/or environment agencies derived from remote sensing data and obtained via other authoritative observations. For this purpose, GREENGAGE technology partners provide a suite of interoperable tools to support needs of specific piloting use cases whereas GREENGAGE's Pilot cities Bristol (the United Kingdom), Copenhagen (Denmark), Turano and Gerace (Italy), and the region of North Brabant (the Netherlands) were and are involved with citizens' engagement, organising CO campaigns, and assist in bottom-up initiatives.

The above-mentioned aim indicates that during the life of the project, diverse data is generated and used. Therefore, GREENGAGE's Data Management Plan (DMP) considers the management of heterogeneous datasets (satellite, urban network of sensors, Open Data) that provide the departure point at each Pilot, plus the privacy-aware trusted crowdsourcing of data coming from citizens and collaborators at the Citizen Observatories set at each Pilot. Given diverse data being collected in the GREENGAGE project, a Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) is done which is elaborated in Deliverable 6.3 (Privacy Impact Assessment).

The report is structured as follows: The first section covers details on GREENGAGE Partners (**Chapter 3**). **Chapter 4** gives overview of GREENGAGE data sources. **Chapter 5** covers roles and responsibilities. Data categories and collection methods are presented in **Chapter 6** whereas **Chapter 7** covers Data organisation and documentation. FAIR principles are covered in **Chapter 8**, data security in **Chapter 9**. Data access, data usage and processing are presented in **Chapters 10 and 11** respectively. GREENGAGE's data preservation, archival, and disposal plan is given in **Chapter 12**, Ethical and Legal Compliance in **Chapter 13**. Details on data register are presented in **Chapter 14**. Finally, **Chapter 15** covers lessons learned and recommendations.

¹ 100 Climate-neutral Cities by 2030 – by and for the Citizens (Sep 2020)

https://ec.europa.eu/info/publications/100-climate-neutral-cities-2030-and-citizens_en

3 GREENGAGE Partners

The GREENGAGE consortium consists of nine technology partners and four city partners.

Technology Partners (in alphabetical order)

- Austrian Institute of Technology (AIT)
- 6 (BUAS)
- Digital Sunray/SushiDev
- GISAT
- HOPU
- MindEarth
- Moondial
- University of Deusto (DEUSTO)
- VRVis

City Partners (in alphabetical order)

- Bristol City Council (The United Kingdom),
- I Borghi piu Belli D'Italia (Turano/Gerace, Italy),
- Miljøpunktamager (Copenhagen, Denmark),
- Noord-Brabant Provincie (North Brabant, The Netherlands)

The University of the West of England (UWE), Bristol UK is responsible for the preparation of DMP. UWE has well defined guidelines for research data management², data protection and security guidelines³, research ethics guidelines⁴, and has a research repository⁵, which was utilised for the GREENGAGE DMP.

Most of the partners had their own procedures for data management, data protection or security policies and ethical guidelines. For example, BUAS has its own data management and ethics guidelines and procedures. Also, all city partners as case studies (or Pilots) have their own internal procedures for data collection, management, and sharing.

Though most partners have their own internal procedures, as the project progressed, project level procedures and guidelines for GREENGAGE Data Management Plan had been formulated.

To avoid any data management related conflicts and to have a harmonised approach for the GREENGAGE project, existing guidelines from the project partners were adapted in line with the European Commission guidelines on Data Management in Horizon Europe⁶. In this respect a questionnaire was shared with partners to fully understand their data management practices. The questionnaire is in Appendix. Several meetings were organised and online collaborative tools (e.g., Miro board) were used to fully understand data flows between different GREENGAGE tools.

² <https://www.uwe.ac.uk/study/library/research-support/manage-your-research-data/planning-your-project/create-a-data-management-plan>

³ <https://www.uwe.ac.uk/about/structure-and-governance/data-protection/data-protection-statement-and-policy>

⁴ <https://www.uwe.ac.uk/research/policies-and-standards/research-ethics/policies-procedures-and-guidance>

⁵ <https://uwe-repository.worktribe.com/>

⁶ <https://enspire.science/data-management-plan-in-horizon-europe/>

4 GREENGAGE Data Sources

The GREEN Engine was designed to ensure that Citizen Observatories are effectively established, and campaigns could be carried out smoothly. The following tools are part of the GREEN Engine: Collaborative Environment, Keycloak, Discourse, Apache Superset, Apache Druid, Apache Nifi, Datahub, Data Quality Dashboard, MODE Library, MindEarth for GREENGAGE app, and GREENGAGE app (these tools are detailed in Deliverable D4.1).

Broadly, there are two sources of data generation in GREENGAGE: (i) GREEN Engine data (Figure 2) (ii) Non-GREEN Engine data (Figure 3). GREEN Engine data entails data collection by GREENGAGE app, MindEarth for GREENGAGE app, Collaborative Environment, KeyCloak, Discourse, and data from External sources such as Atmotube, 3rd party data, open data, Copernicus data, and government data.

GREENGAGE Engine Data

Figure 2: GREEN Engine data and sources

Non GREENGAGE Engine Data

Figure 3: Non-GREEN Engine data and sources

Non-GREENGAGE data includes data collection from workshops, interviews, walks, focus groups, and surveys by Pilots. Mostly this category represents qualitative data. Chapters 6 and 7 presents details on data categories, data organisation, and data collection.

5 Roles and Responsibilities

Concerning the responsibilities for the GREENGAGE DMP, the following roles have been identified:

- (i) **Data Controllers:** Responsible for protecting the data lifecycle i.e., from collection to processing, storage, security, and sharing. They also define purpose and means of data processing.
- (ii) **Joint Controllers:** In the context of GREENGAGE project, joint controllers are two or more partners who jointly manage GREENGAGE data including determining the purposes and means of the data processing.
- (iii) **Data Processors:** Partners performing data processing on behalf of a controller act as processors; their actions are under the control and documented instructions of the controller.
- (iv) **Data Consumers:** Users of existing or new (processed) data

Data Controllers:

The GREENGAGE project has joint-controllers to define the purpose and means of processing and storage.

The purpose of data and processing is jointly defined by Pilot owners (Bristol, Copenhagen, Gerace, Turano, and North Brabant) and GREEN Engine technology providers to serve the data and processing needs of Pilot case studies.

In this context Bristol, Copenhagen, Borghi (for Turano and Gerace) and North Brabant are joint controllers with AIT, DEUSTO, SushiDev, DigitalSunray, MindEarth, VRViS, HOPU, BUAS, and UWE.

More specifically, we list individual and joint responsibilities for various GREENGAGE related data sets as below:

- (i) Controllers / Joint Controllers for GREEN Engine Data

As stated in Chapter 4, GREEN Engine integrates several tools, and the data being generated by these tools are jointly controlled by MindEarth, DEUSTO, SushiDev, and VRViS.

- MindEarth - manages the data lifecycle (collection, pre-processing, analysis, visualisation) that is being collected by the MindEarth for GREENGAGE app.
- DEUSTO - manages the data lifecycle that is being collected through KeyCloak (sign up web page and consent), Collaborative Environment, and Discourse.
- SushiDev, DEUSTO, and VRViS are jointly responsible for managing the GREENGAGE app data. Their roles are as follows:
 - SushiDev - Storing and managing data of GREENGAGE app / api control instance.
 - DEUSTO - Managing consent and single-sign-on through KeyCloak server hosted and managed by DEUSTO.
 - VRViS - Hosts and manage Apache Superset, Apache Druid, Apache Nifi, DataHub, and Data Quality Dashboard.

- (ii) Controllers / Joint Controllers for Non-GREEN Engine Data:

- Bristol, Turano, Gerace, Copenhagen, and North Brabant are controllers of non-GREEN Engine data for their Pilots. They collect non-GREEN Engine data produced through workshops, interviews, surveys and walks.
 - Pilot owners collect raw data, and only anonymised or aggregated data from non-GREEN Engine data is stored on UWE OneDrive; details on how UWE is managing the data on UWE OneDrive is presented in Chapter 9 of this document.
 - BUAS-joint controller with North Brabant. BUAS is storing and managing North Brabant data.

(iii) Controllers / Joint Controllers for Other data types:

- For other data types e.g., external surveys, UWE is joint controller with AIT and BUAS to carry out survey on city governance models for Citizen Observatories, as part of task T2.4 (December 2024).
- Borghi is controller for mobility data purchased through 3rd parties for Turano valley

Data Processors of GREENGAGE are UWE, BUAS, VIRViS, MindEarth, SushiDev, DEUSTO, AIT, and Pilot owners. Their roles are:

- UWE is responsible for analysis of data (Dashcam video analytics), sentiments, and summarisation of qualitative survey data.
- BUAS is responsible for access to DigiTwin shell into which the data from the data producers is integrated. BUAS analyse travel patterns in DigiTwin.
- VRViS analyses data from GREENGAGE central storage Druid and visualises it using Visual Dashboard
- MindEarth analyses data from the MindEarth for GREENGAGE app, dashcam videos, and mobility data from 3rd parties
- SushiDev processes user input through the GREENGAGE app API and make it accessible/available via the GraphQL Endpoint
- DEUSTO analyses evaluation and impact assessment survey data
- AIT, UWE and BUAS analyse governance survey data.
- Pilot owners (Bristol, Copenhagen, Gerace, Turano and North Brabant) also analyse data from workshops, surveys, walks and interviews.

Data Consumers are public authorities, citizens, and other research organisations interested in CO data.

6 Data Categories and Collection Method

Within the GREENGAGE project, various datasets are processed and generated, encompassing different categories of data. These datasets are intended to serve specific purposes and contribute to the project's objectives. Broadly, the data is categorised as personal and non-personal data. Personal data is broadly collected through (i) GREEN Engine login and GPS tracking (ii) interviews and surveys conducted by Pilots. Before data collection, a Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) was performed. Both EU⁷ and UK⁸ guidelines/templates for DPIA were followed. Deliverable D6.3 (Privacy Impact Assessment) will cover further details.

As stated in chapter 4, GREENGAGE collects data from two sources (i) GREEN Engine (ii) Non-GREEN Engine sources such as workshops, interviews, walks, focus groups, and surveys by Pilots. Both sources will generate personal as well as non-personal data:

1. **Personal data:** Types of personal data that is collected in the context of the project is as follows:
 - a. **Data contributors and users of the applications.** The personal data involve username, first name, last name, email address, password, profile picture, GREENGAGE ID, Observatory ID. Sociodemographic data also includes language, acquaintance level of digital tools, role in the co-production process, age range, social/disadvantaged group, education level, gender, and type of organisation to which the user belongs, work status, and city where the user lives is also collected. The login data (email address, username and password) is required to provide a single-sign-on to different GREEN Engine tools e.g., GREENGAGE app, MindEarth for GREENGAGE app, Collaborative Environment, Superset etc. The sociodemographic data is collected to measure statistical Key Performance Indicators i.e., number of users signed up and using the GREEN Engine, number of users signed up from different age group and social groups to assess level of inclusivity in GREENGAGE COs.
 - b. **From Citizens as active sensors.** This mainly includes data collected from GPS tracking such as users' location (Geographical GPS Coordinates (e.g., Spots in the GREENGAGE app)). GPS tracking information in form of AIT MODE Binary data (which will be transformed into GeoJSON). The GREENGAGE app is also collecting images of Spots from users and experiment related task data e.g., answering pre-defined questions related to a specific Point of Interest (POI). Similarly, MindEarth for GREENGAGE app and Atmotube sensors collect GPS linked data. Citizen data such as GPS location is used to verify adherence to mission brief, to verify quality of collected data and geo-locate features extracted from anonymised imagery.
 - c. **Survey Data.** This data is collected by the GREENGAGE app and by Pilots. The Pilots' data mainly includes socio-demographic data in line with Pilot owners' set organisational procedures. For example, Bristol City Council gathers such data as per their equality considerations for standard survey or consultation procedures. This data may include personal data: Age, Disability, Ethnicity, Religion / Faith, Sex / Gender, Pregnancy, Career Status, Refugee or Asylum Seeker Status, Nationality, Marriage / Civil Partnership Status, Postcode, Place of Residence information. Both Borghi Più Belli d'Italia and Bristol City Council also collect special category data -Racial / Ethnic Origin, Religion or Philosophical Beliefs, Trade Union membership, Health, Sexual orientation. The Pilots collect the personal data to include representative samples and ensure data quality. For privacy and confidentiality, none of these personal data are shared with the rest of the consortium partners or any 3rd party. This data is required to ensure engagement with under-represented groups is achieved. For example, North-Brabant collects personal data to highlight contrasts in age or gender to illustrate the varied nature of maintenance requirements such as to improve the road infrastructure and make biking more appealing; understanding these differences can lead to a more target-audience approach. Survey Data is used to determine the base data, POIs, formulation of research questions, usability of tools and impact of GREENGAGE. GREENGAGE Pilot owners have been using both online and paper-based approaches to collect survey, workshops, walks, and interview data. For

⁷ <https://gdpr.eu/data-protection-impact-assessment-template/>

⁸ <https://gdpr.eu/wp-content/uploads/2019/03/dpia-template-v1.pdf>

online surveys, EU Survey⁹ (by European Commission), MS forms, Google forms or Qualtrics are used to collect the responses. Personal data collected by Pilots is handled as per their set defined procedures and policies and not shared with the GREENGAGE project. Thus, this personal data is not collected, processed, and handled by the GREENGAGE project.

- d. **Interview data.** With the help of Pilot Support teams (PSTs), Pilot owners conducted interviews and focus group meetings with citizen observers and other stakeholders (e.g., local businesses), to seek their viewpoints about the GREENGAGE innovation Pilots and Citizen Observatories. The focus was on the usability, the benefits of GREENGAGE Citizen Observatory and what practical implications there are to sustain these COs in future. BUAS manages the North Brabant data and interviews data from other Pilots are stored on UWE OneDrive. Manual notes and recordings are done by using GDPR compliant tools such as UWE MS Teams or other GDPR compliant mobile recording devices.

Given the importance of personal data protection and privacy in the context of GREENGAGE such concerns were considered as early as the **design phase so that strict data protection policies could be established**. Chapter 9 (Data Security) elaborates how personal data was handled in GREENGAGE.

2. **Non-personal Data:** GREENGAGE collects and processes a large amount of non-personal data, stated as below.
 - a. **Experiment or Mission Data:** Users of the MindEarth for GREENGAGE app can create, book, and cancel missions. Missions' data include Longitude and Latitude information of each mission's starting points, mission path, mission ID, duration of mission, series of images at regular interval, dashcam video (series of frames), etc.
 - b. **Street Qualitative Data:** users of GREENGAGE app can specify Spots, answer questions and upload images as part of tasks at a POI, which is qualitative data.
 - c. **Co-production data:** the co-production processes, through Collaborative Environment, collect assets such as documents, images or links to external websites. User comments and discussions are collected through Discourse.
 - d. **Platform usage and User Statistics:** Statistics information include the number of users who completed a task in GREENGAGE app or completed a mission in the MindEarth for GREENGAGE app.
 - e. **Community observations** were used to improve existing Earth Observation models. For example, the mobile sensor (Atmotube) for air quality monitoring, roads safety status through dashcam videos in Gerace and Turano.
 - f. **Government and open datasets:** In addition to above data that is generated in GREENGAGE, the project used government and open datasets. For example, the data used by Bristol included accident type data etc. Further, satellite and Earth Observations data were used to cross-validate in-situ CO observations and/or to complement data that otherwise could not be gathered through the GREEN Engine tools.
 - g. **External data sources** such as Atmotube as mobile air quality sensor to collect selected pollutants.

Crowdsourced data is captured by the GREENGAGE app, MindEarth for GREENGAGE app, Collaborative Environment, Discourse, Atmotube, and Dashcams.

GREEN Engine is using <https://me.greengage-project.eu> sign up process that provides single sign on option. The credentials of users are managed by a KeyCloak authentication server and data is collected and managed by DEUSTO. The data collected by KeyCloak is also used to acquire data on platform usage and user statistics. As the website collects personal data, data protection and security measures are applied (details are presented in the Chapter 9). All experimental data is stored in the GREENGAGE central storage called Apache Druid.

⁹ <https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/home/welcome>

7 Data Organisation and Documentation

GREENGAGE organises data at two levels (i) Partner level (ii) Project level.

- (i) **Non-GREEN Engine data** such as interviews, focus groups, surveys and walks data is first stored on Pilots' local storage which is then anonymised and later transferred to UWE's OneDrive secure storage; for North Brabant, BUAS is managing their data. The following Table 1 presents a summary of non-GREEN Engine datasets.

Table 1: Non-GREEN Engine data / output generated through the project.

Dataset Name	WP	Contact	Origin	Size (Estimated)	Format	Privacy	Access Type	License ¹⁰
Use cases and requirements	WP2	UWE	Workshops / Survey with Pilot owners	< 5 MB	Report	NA	Public via D2.2 / project website / Zenodo	*
Governance models	WP2	UWE	Workshops / Survey with Pilot owners	< 5 MB	Report	NA	Public via D2.4 / project website / Zenodo	*
User evaluation and impact survey	WP6	DEUSTO	Questionnaire with Pilot owners	< 5MB	Report	GREEN GAGE ID	Anonymous data will be public via D6.5 / project website / Zenodo	*
Governance Survey	WP2	AIT / UWE	Online survey with stakeholders	<5MB	Report	Email, Name	Anonymous data will be public via D2.5 / project website / Zenodo	*
Usage statistics	WP6	AIT	GREEN Engine usage	<5MB	Quantitative	GREEN GAGE ID	Anonymous data will be public via project website	*
Participation statistics	WP5	IBERCIVIS	Workshop / Walks	<5MB	Quantitative	Name, contact, demographic	Anonymous data will be public via project website	*
Datathons	WP7	KWMC	Workshops	10MB to 1GB	Report	GREEN GAGE ID	Anonymous data will be public via project website	*
Training material as part of GREENGAGE academy	WP5	IBERCIVIS	Project Domain Experts	Up to 1 GB	Videos	Trainer details		*
GREEN Engine Documentation	WP4	DEUSTO	Tech providers	<5 MB	Text / online	Anonymous	Public	Apache 2.0

* As part of task 7.15, there are ongoing discussions regarding the sustainability and replication of the project.

¹⁰ - * License for some of the datasets will be decided as part of the sustainability and replication strategy in [Deliverable D7.15 – Replication and Sustainability Roadmap V2](#).

- (ii) **GREEN Engine data** is also first captured at local storage of DEUSTO, MindEarth, and SushiDev which is then sent to GREENGAGE common central storage i.e., Apache Druid (located in Vienna).

Figure 4 shows GREENGAGE's conceptual model.

Figure 4: GREENGAGE Conceptual Model

As shown in the Figure 4, GREENGAGE collects and manages various data sets from different GREEN Engine tools. GREENGAGE datasets have various data schemas which are comprehensive and quite rich in content. Hence, the figure shows the data organisation at a conceptual level. Figure 5 shows the data flow diagram of the GREEN Engine and the overall view of the data flow among GREENGAGE's tools. Figure 6 shows data flow of non-GREEN Engine data i.e., data being managed by Pilots. Tables 2 through 7 below show details of the datasets. They also hold the links to the respective data schemas.

Figure 5: GREEN Engine data flow overview

Figure 6: Other data flow overview

1. Visual Street Mission Datasets

Table 2: Visual Street Mission Datasets Description

Name of the Datasets	Visual Street Mission Data
Category of Data	Personal as well as non-personal
If personal, how is the data managed?	Anonymised and not shared with public or partners
Short Description of the dataset	Users of the MindEarth for GREENGAGE app can create, book, and cancel missions. Missions' data include Longitude and Latitude information of each mission's starting points, mission path, mission ID, duration of mission, series of images at regular interval, etc.
Format of the dataset	Image data: JPEG (.jpg) or GeoTIFF (.geotiff). Spatial Data Distribution: Shapefile (.shp), GeoPackage (.gpkg), or GeoJSON [(geojson). Time-series data: Comma-Separated Values (.csv) or JSON (.json).
Data Storage	Local server and then summarised data on Apache Druid
Estimated size of dataset (e.g., per record, per Pilot, collective GREENGAGE level data size)	Photographic imagery: 5-10 mb per image Curated geo-data layer: 20-40 mb
Source of the dataset	MindEarth for GREENGAGE app
Data Controller	MindEarth
Data origin	Same as source
Restriction	Personal data is kept private Raw and anonymised photographic imagery is kept private.
How the data is accessible? (Would it be available in public repository? Or Authorisation/authentication might be required?)	Photographic imagery: only accessible to data controller, not shared on public repository Curated geo-data layer: accessible via public repository to part of GREENGAGE data infrastructure
Under which license is the dataset accessible?	Curated geo-data layer: Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike (CC BY SA)
Metadata standards	Metadata associated with the collected data will include information about the data's origin, collection methods, and processing steps as well as details such as the date and time of collection, location coordinates, survey device specifications, accuracy of selected KPI, and other relevant information agreed with Pilot cities.

2. Visual Road Dashcam Datasets

Table 3: Visual Road Dashcam Dataset Description

Name of the Datasets	Visual Road Dashcam Data
Category of Data	Personal as well as non-personal
If personal, how is the data managed?	Anonymised and not shared with public or partners
Short Description of the dataset	Dashcam video recordings of selected roads of Gerace and Turano to automatically detect road defects (e.g., potholes, hazards, etc.) and generate street healthy index
Format of the dataset	Collection of videos with geo-tagging and timestamp
Data Storage	MindEarth Storage

Estimated size of dataset (e.g., per record, per Pilot, collective GREENGAGE level data size)	Photographic imagery: 5-8 mb per image Curated geo-data layer: 20-40 mb
Source of the dataset	Dashcams
Data Controller	Borghi and MindEarth
Data origin	Same as source
Restriction	Photographic imagery is kept private until fully anonymised
How the data is accessible? (Would it be available in public repository? Or Authorisation/authentication might be required?)	Photographic imagery: only accessible anonymisation, afterwards shared to authorised users. Curated geo-data layer: accessible via public repository to part of GREENGAGE data infrastructure
Under which license is the dataset accessible?	Photographic imagery: Restricted License Curated geo-data layer: Creative Commons Attribution-ShareAlike (CC BY SA)
Metadata standards	Metadata associated with the collected data will include information about the data's origin, collection methods, and processing steps as well as details such as the date and time of collection, location coordinates, survey device specifications, accuracy of selected KPI, and other relevant information agreed with Pilot cities.

3. Street Qualitative Survey Datasets

Table 4: Street Qualitative Survey Dataset Description

Name of the Datasets	Street Qualitative Survey Data sets
Category of Data	Non-personal
If personal, how is data managed?	N/A
Short Description of the dataset	Users of GREENGAGE app can do tasks (e.g., surveys) and create Spots. Street Qualitative datasets include city information, tasks, mission data, user textual data and/or survey (or task) questions response data, geotagged spots
Link to Dataset Schema	https://api-v2.GREENGAGE.dev/cp
Format of the dataset	The data is provided as JSON. Specific parts of the structure are provided as GeoJSON + additional information like images are provided in the raw (uploaded) data format.
Data Storage	SushiDev infrastructure (PSQL + S3-Storage) and then summarised data on Apache Druid
Estimated size of dataset (e.g., per record, per Pilot, collective GREENGAGE level data size)	>5 GB (including uploaded images)
Source of the dataset	GREENGAGE app
Data Controller	SushiDev
Data origin	Same as source
Restriction on data usage	No restrictions / Provider wise
How the data is accessible? (Would it be available in public repository? Or Authorisation/authentication might be required?)	The dataset is accessible to the authorised user via a standard web serviced API. Deeper administrations and mutation permissions are only available for the observatory. The https://console-stage.greengage.dev backend site provides insights for the data and the application allows download and review of the data.
Under which license is the dataset accessible?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Version 1 of the application is under Fair software tier

- Version 2 is a SaaS solution with a free tier.

Metadata standards	The metadata for the datasets are described using the minimum required (compulsory) elements as recommended in section 8.
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4. Co-production Datasets

Table 5: Co-production Dataset Description

Name of the Datasets	Co-production process
Category of Data	Personal and non-personal
If personal, how is data managed?	Pseudonymisation
Short Description of the dataset	Co-production data includes data related to GREENGAGE ID, documents, topics discussions, and details on co-production processes.
Link to Dataset Schema	Collaborative Environment: Data model — Interlink documentation Discourse: Discourse - dbdiagram.io
Format of the dataset	Any kind of file for the documents for the Collaborative Environment (CE). Tabular data for discourse and CE's co-production processes
Data Storage	DEUSTO server and then summarised data on Apache Druid (secure storage)
Estimated size of dataset (e.g., per record, per Pilot, collective GREENGAGE level data size)	The size depends on the documents added on the co-production process and the conversations on Discourse
Source of the dataset	Collaborative Environment and Discourse
Data Controller	DEUSTO
Data origin	Same as source
Restriction on data usage	Personal data is kept private
How the data is accessible? (Would it be available in public repository? Or Authorisation/authentication might be required?)	Data will be only accessible for the authorised users. In the CE, the authorised users may be users in the same team as the owner of the data. Furthermore, co-production processes can be published in the catalogue of success stories.
Under which license is the dataset accessible?	Private dataset
Metadata standards	N/A

5. User Demographic Datasets

Table 6: User Demographic Dataset Description

Name of the Datasets	User demographic dataset
Category of Data	Personal
If personal, how is data managed?	Pseudonymisation
Short Description of the dataset	Through me.greengage-project.eu , user demographic data is collected. The data mainly include email address, age range, gender, organisation, work status, education, location.
Link to Dataset Schema	Keycloak: KeyCloak - dbdiagram.io
Format of the dataset	Tabular data
Data Storage	DEUSTO server (secure storage)

Estimated size of dataset (e.g., per record, per Pilot, collective GREENGAGE level data size)	20kb per user
Source of the dataset	KeyCloak
Data Controller	DEUSTO
Data origin	Same as source
Restriction on data usage	Personal data is not accessible to public or partners
How the data is accessible? (Would it be available in public repository? Or Authorisation/authentication might be required?)	N/A
Under which license is the dataset accessible?	N/A
Metadata standards	Keycloak uses SAML 2.0, OpenID Connect Discovery 1.0, RFC 8414 and UMA 2.0 metadata standards.

6. Community Air Quality Observation Datasets

Table 7: Community Observation Dataset Description

Name of the Datasets	Air quality data
Category of Data	Non-personal
If personal, how is data managed?	N/A
Short Description of the dataset	The data captured by Atmotube includes AtmotubeID (in form of the device's MAC address), details regarding air pollutants, and geocoordinates
Link to Dataset Schema	cloud api 1.2 Atmotube SwaggerHub
Format of the dataset	Tabular or JSON
Data Storage	External Storage by Atmotube (GREENGAGE is not managing Atmotube data). As secondary source, some data such as coordinates, air pollutants, atmotubeID is collected from external storage stored in Apache Druid.
Estimated size of dataset (e.g., per record, per Pilot, collective GREENGAGE level data size)	Avg. Row size (bytes): 11
Source of the dataset	Atmotube
Data Controller	DEUSTO, VRViS
Data origin	Same as source
Restriction on data usage	N/A
How the data is accessible? (Would it be available in public repository? Or Authorisation/authentication might be required?)	Authorisation/authentication required
Under which license is the dataset accessible?	N/A
Metadata standards	N/A

Other datasets GREENGAGE project reused/plans to reuse from other existing sources

Table 8: Other existing datasets which were/will be (re)used within the GREENGAGE project

Dataset Name	WP	Contact	Origin	Format	Privacy	Access Type
Copernicus (Sentinel 2)	WP4	GISAT	Copernicus	Geo-spatial	Anonymised	Public data / analysed results will be public
Open Data Portal	WP4	DEUSTO / VRVIS	Bristol Open Data Portal (BODP)	CSV	Anonymised	Analysed results will be public
Mobility Data	WP4	MindEarth	Proprietary	CSV / parquet / GeoJSON	Anonymised	Analysed results will be public
Copenhagen authoritative data	WP4	DEUSTO	Aqicn	CSV	Anonymised	Extracted from Aqicn / analysed results might be public (Subject to license)

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8 FAIR Principles

This section outlines how FAIR principles are incorporated for Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability for the data that is generated and used within GREENGAGE.

1. Findability

Findability refers to the ability of the data to be easily discovered by both humans and machines. Making data findable is a foundational step in ensuring it can be effectively reused.

- All the necessary datasets will be made available with globally unique and persistent identifiers (e.g. Digital Object Identifiers) via domain specific or general purpose repositories (e.g., Zenodo) to facilitate data discovery. These identifiers will provide a stable link to the datasets and makes it easy to find them in the long term. Moreover, publishing those datasets on the online repositories will make it visible to broader audience as it will be indexed by major search engines which facilitates easy discovery of the datasets.
- Rich metadata is vital for the context and the understanding of the datasets. Therefore, the metadata will use structural information to describe the datasets and explicitly include the persistent identifier.
- Broadly standardised metadata schema will be used to describe the datasets to ensure that the metadata is easily read and understood by the machines. Domain specific/general metadata standard or the metadata schema of the online repository will be used to describe most of the datasets. While it is important to choose a metadata standard that associates well with the nature of the datasets, a few metadata standards are identified and recommended to be used based on partner's and requirements and the type of data sets project generates.

Recommendations

- [ISO-19115](#) is an internationally adopted and widely used geographic metadata standard for describing geographic information and services.
- [DataCite](#) is a standardised framework for interdisciplinary data. The schema contains a list of core metadata properties to ensure that datasets are properly described with key information.
- [Dublin Core Metadata Element Set](#) is a standardised metadata schema used to describe a resource and valued for its generalised structure with fifteen properties that can be used to discover and link the data.
- [DDI \(Data Documentation Initiative\)](#) is an international metadata standard which can describe variable level datasets applicable for surveys and observational methods in social, behavioural, and other sciences.

If no specific metadata standard is used, the datasets of GREENGAGE should be described with the following elements:

Compulsory:

- Title
- Creator/Author
- Subject/keywords
- Description of the dataset
- Publisher
- Date
- Source/input data/parameter used to generate data

- Persistent Identifier (e.g. DOI)
- Data usage license
- Funding Grant name and Number as below: The GREENGAGE project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme (grant agreement n° 101086530). This work was co-funded by UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government’s Horizon Europe funding guarantee 10063933, 10062587, 10064231. This work was co-funded by SERI (State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation) under the funding ID Contract No. 22.00496 REF-131-52014.

Recommended (to be included, where possible):

- Version
- Language
- Date of metadata creation
- Encoding techniques
- Access rights management
- Provenance information/History

To provide researcher/users with a centralized and easily accessible overview of the project, additional measures will be implemented, including the creation of a **CSV-based project catalogue**. This catalogue will contain essential metadata for each dataset, including the dataset **name, type, DOI** (Digital Object Identifier), **authors, brief description, and license information**. By including these key elements, the catalogue will enhance data discoverability and ensure that researchers/users can quickly find relevant datasets with sufficient context to assess their needs.

2. Accessibility

Accessibility refers to how easily data can be accessed once it has been found. Accessibility focuses on ensuring that the data is available and clear access mechanisms are in place.

- Necessary datasets including research results will be made available with persistent identifiers (e.g. Digital Object Identifiers) via domain specific repositories or general purpose repositories (e.g. Zenodo) which will make them available publicly making them accessible to everyone for reuse.
- For accessibility of data and scientific publications there are some recommendations made:

Recommendation

- Open access data repository (domain specific/general purpose) should be used for uploading data under the public licence (e.g. CC) or a licence with equivalent rights.
- Machine readable version of the scientific publication or the final peer reviewed accepted manuscript should be deposited to the trusted repository with an open access under public license (e.g. CC) or equivalent.
- Provide information about the research, research data, and associated tools
- Provide a data availability statement with detailed information about where and how the data can be accessed
- Metadata should be available even when the data is no longer available

- There are certain datasets that cannot be made public e.g. Non-GREEN Engine sources such as workshops, interviews, walks, focus group, and surveys to which data protection and security measures are applied and will have restricted access.

- Personal data that is collected through GREEN Engine will not be shared to protect privacy of the participants

3. Interoperability

Interoperability refers to the ability of data to be integrated or used with other datasets or tools or systems. **Interoperability** facilitates the integration of data across different platforms and ensures that different systems can work together.

To ensure interoperability, data will be described using **rich metadata schemas** and the data shall use standardised formats (e.g. JSON, CSV, GeoJSON). Using machine readable file formats, structured metadata, and open-access repositories will ensure that the data is accessible, retrievable and usable with other systems and tools. There are certain recommendations made regarding data file formats:

Recommendation

- CSV format for tabular data
- GeoPackage or GeoJSON for vector data

4. Reusability

Reusability focuses on making data suitable for reuse by others, ensuring that it is well-documented, properly licensed, and in a format that can be understood.

- Accurate, relevant, structured, and well described metadata will be provided for datasets which will help users to understand the context, the content and how it was generated.
- For the data to be reusable, it is important that the data is compatible with other systems and tool, which means, the data will be provided in a machine-readable format (e.g. JSON, CSV, GeoJSON).
- Appropriate license information will be made explicit in the metadata for dataset access and reuse as applicable.
- Additionally, there are certain recommendations made to maximise reuse.

Recommendation

Providing additional README files with information including:

- Data provenance
- Data origin
- Data provider
- Data processing details
- Date of retrieval
- License of use
- DOI
- File History

Table 9 summarises datasets/deliverables/publications that are publicly available till date. Given the project is still ongoing, more deliverables/datasets will be made publicly available at a later time.

Table 9: Publicly available Project Deliverables, Journal Articles, Conference Papers, and Datasets.

Title of Deliverable	Type	Link	License	Access Condition
Participatory Design of Visual Analytics Tools for Different Target Groups	Journal Article	https://zenodo.org/records/15533351	Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International	Public
Empowering Urban Transformation: The Role of Citizen Observatories in Inclusive and Data-Driven Governance	Conference Paper	https://zenodo.org/records/15387716	Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International	Public
Datasets collected from a GREENGAGE's thematic co-exploration for Bilbao campus at University of DEUSTO	Datasets	https://zenodo.org/records/15195849	Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International	Public
Towards a Methodological Framework for Citizen Observatories to Promote Inclusive Urban Governance	Conference Proceedings	https://zenodo.org/records/14711633	Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International	Public
Performance Assessment of Wearable Atmotube Pro Sensor for Air Quality Citizen Science Applications	Conference Paper	https://zenodo.org/records/13354677	Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International	Public
Democratizing Co-production of Thematic Co-explorations for Citizen Observatories	Conference Paper	https://zenodo.org/records/13354463	Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International	Public
Designing Interactive Analytics Dashboards for Diverse Target Groups: The Process and Decision-Making	Conference Paper	https://zenodo.org/records/13354619	Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International	Public
GREEN Engine Documentation	Technical Guide	https://GREENGAGE-E-project.github.io/Documentation/	Apache 2.0	Public
GREENGAGE App API Docs	Technical Guide	https://docs-stage.GREENGAGE.dev/docs	MIT	Public
WP1 D1.11 Data Management Plan 1	Project Deliverable	https://zenodo.org/records/15749928	Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International	Public

WP2 D2.1 GREENGAGE Citizen Observatories Methodological Framework	Project Deliverable	https://zenodo.org/records/15739095	Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International	Public
WP2 D2.2 Use Cases and Requirements Analysis 1	Project Deliverable	Check later version: https://zenodo.org/records/15754799	Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International	Public
WP2 D2.3 Use Cases and Requirements Analysis 2	Project Deliverable	https://zenodo.org/records/15754799	Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International	Public
WP2 D2.4 Smart Governance Models 1	Project Deliverable	https://zenodo.org/records/15739194	Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International	Public
WP2 D2.6 GREENGAGE Technological Requirements 1	Project Deliverable	Check later version: https://zenodo.org/records/15754820	Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International	Public
WP2 D2.7 GREENGAGE Technological Requirements 2	Project Deliverable	https://zenodo.org/records/15754820	Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International	Public
WP3 D3.1 Citizen Observer Training: "How to do Research" and CO Toolbox	Project Deliverable	https://zenodo.org/records/15743851	Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International	Public
WP3 D3.2 CO solution mapping to Pilots, recruitment and training report	Project Deliverable	https://zenodo.org/records/15743873	Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International	Public
WP3 D3.3 GREENGAGE CO Academy Roadmap	Project Deliverable	https://zenodo.org/records/15743884	Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International	Public
WP4 D4.1 GREEN Engine and manual 1	Project Deliverable	Check later version: https://zenodo.org/records/15754756	Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International	Public
WP4 D4.2 GREEN Engine and manual 2	Project Deliverable	https://zenodo.org/records/15754756	Creative Commons Attribution	Public

			4.0 International	
WP D4.3 GREENGAGE interoperable tools for urban analytics data to policy workflow lifecycle 1	Project Deliverable	https://zenodo.org/records/15750176	Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International	Public
WP4 D4.5 GREENGAGE experiment and monitoring system and manual 1	Project Deliverable	https://zenodo.org/records/15750201	Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International	Public
WP5 D5.3 Training and Campaigning Report and Community Building 1	Project Deliverable	https://zenodo.org/records/15744008	Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International	Public
WP5 D5.5 GREENGAGE CO Academy Structured Content 1	Project Deliverable	https://zenodo.org/records/15744076	Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International	Public
WP6 D6.5 Impact Assessment Report 1	Project Deliverable	https://zenodo.org/records/15750234	Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International	Public
WP6 D6.7 GREENGAGE based Citizen Observatory: White Book for PAs 1	Project Deliverable	https://zenodo.org/records/15754939	Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International	Public
WP7 D7.4 Project identity and branding	Project Deliverable	https://zenodo.org/records/15750264	Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International	Public
WP7 D7.5 Project Website and Social Media Platforms	Project Deliverable	https://zenodo.org/records/15744199	Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International	Public
WP7 D7.6 Package of dissemination materials 1	Project Deliverable	Check later version: https://zenodo.org/records/15754984	Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International	Public
WP7 D7.7 Package of dissemination materials 2	Project Deliverable	Check later version: https://zenodo.org/records/15754984	Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International	Public

WP7 D7.8 Package of dissemination materials 3	Project Deliverable	https://zenodo.org/records/15754984	Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International	Public
WP7 D7.10 Creation of International Community of Citizen Observers 1	Project Deliverable	https://zenodo.org/records/15744285	Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International	Public
WP7 D7.12 Citizen Observers' exchange programme 1	Project Deliverable	https://zenodo.org/records/15750394	Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International	Public

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9 Data Security

Data security measures are defined for both GREEN Engine and Non-GREEN Engine data sources. For both types of data, data security measures are applied at data collection, sharing, storage, and access.

Non-GREEN Engine data

As stated in chapter 6, Pilots are using both online and paper-based approaches to collect survey, workshops, walks, and interview data. For paper-based approaches Pilots store the data in physical folders in secure cabinets. The folders can only be accessed by associated researchers.

Anonymised and/or aggregated data is to be kept on UWE's OneDrive. Therefore, UWE has defined the folder structure on their OneDrive where data is stored. Only selected GREENGAGE partners have access to those folders.

The personal data (e.g., age group, gender etc.) which are gathered in surveys will be aggregated and pseudonymised (which are linked with DEUSTO's KeyCloak) or anonymised (which are not linked with DEUSTO's KeyCloak) to protect privacy. Data stored on UWE's OneDrive is in aggregated form and no personal data is stored. Digital copies of consent forms are also stored on UWE's OneDrive folders. Only Pilot owners and selected UWE staff has access to the consent forms folder. Further, different access levels are provided to these folders depending on co-researchers' needs. Partners are using strong encryption techniques when transferring or sharing data via a network and data files should be password protected.

North Brabant data is managed by BUAS. During the research, raw and processed data is stored on the BUAS Research Drive (BUAS branded instance of SURF Research Drive). This secure environment has been specially created for storage, meeting the BUAS Regulation pertaining to Research Data Management. Physical data, such as the paper-based signed consent forms, are stored in physical folders in locked cabinets, only accessible to associated researchers (like digital data). Finally, they are digitised and added to the BUAS Research Drive as Data Documentation.

GREEN Engine data

To apply the privacy by design principle, the *pseudonymisation* data technique¹¹ is used to protect privacy of participants. Rather than having fully anonymous records, each record is associated with the participants' unique ID (in GREENGAGE it is called GREENGAGE ID). Participant credentials are managed by KeyCloak. Once the data is analysed/summarised then the data will be anonymous and cannot be traced back to the participants. As a rule of thumb, no personal data will be made available in the public domain to ensure that privacy of participants is protected. Only anonymised data will be published. Personal data captured using GREEN Engine is managed by KeyCloak. No personal data will be transferred to GREENGAGE's project central data repository Apache Druid except the GREENGAGE ID. Only selected GREENGAGE partners have access to the KeyCloak storage.

In addition to the above security measures, the additional measures are applied to datasets and are detailed as follows:

The MindEarth for GREENGAGE app mission data: to collect data in the MindEarth for GREENGAGE app the following security measures have been applied:

Encryption: All images collected through the MindEarth for GREENGAGE app are immediately locally encrypted before being securely transmitted to the cloud server for anonymisation, deletion and storage. This prevents any misuse of locally stored data.

Restricted access. Access to collected anonymised data and data processing tasks are restricted to authorised MindEarth personnel, via specific software-authorized machines using a strict authentication method (i.e., access key) at specific locations (i.e., as identified by their IP address). Unique authentication credentials and/or a strong password associated to each authorised user are required to access and process data.

¹¹ <http://www.pseudonymised.com/>

Security at Access Level: raw, unprotected street-level imagery is not retained or shared with any third parties, including members of the GREENGAGE consortium.

For **street quality survey** data, the GREENGAGE app relies on numerous industry standards (such as Claim-Based Authentication) to ensure data integrity within the overall context. With the rollout of version 2 of the GREENGAGE app infrastructure, data is now split into individual observatories, each of which can manage its own data independently. This ensures that observatory administrators can monitor and verify data quality themselves. Interventions by external third parties without contextual understanding are therefore prevented. In addition to common features like HTTPS connections, there are also content-specific mechanisms for COs to supervise data integrity qualitatively and, most importantly, collaboratively (e.g., Validation tasks/missions). Authentications wise, the GREENGAGE app, by default, integrates the Key Cloak and Username/Password mechanisms. Endpoint wise any data mutation need to be authenticated via a JWT (JSON Web Token) (token lifetime = 5 minutes). In terms of client-based applications like the admin panel the transport of the token is done via JWE (JSON Web Encryption), which is a feasible and secure.

Community air quality observations (such as by Atmotube): Atmotube data security measures are covered in their privacy policy: <https://atmotube.com/privacy>. GREENGAGE retrieves device specific data from Atmotube cloud storage by using unique API key and HTTPs protocol. API key is received by registering physical address and serial number of the sensor, see details here: <https://atmotube.com/atmotube-support/atmotube-cloud-api>.

Co-production data (by Collaborative Environment): the data is password protected and personal data such as email can only be accessed by authorised users. The **Discourse** platform prioritises data security by hosting the service on a secure AWS server located in the European Union. Access to the platform is exclusively via HTTPS, ensuring encrypted communication, and is protected through OAuth authentication provided by KeyCloak for robust identity and access management. Data collected includes essential personal information such as usernames, email addresses, and optional profile details, along with user-published topic data. Sensitive information like email addresses is treated as strictly confidential, while public-facing data is visible to platform participants. The platform complies with GDPR by minimising data collection and retaining user information only as long as necessary. Users are informed of their data protection rights and can manage their data through a control panel, ensuring a secure and privacy-compliant experience.

10 Data Access

REENGAGE follows the principle of data being “as open as possible as closed as necessary”. Only the project coordinator and designated representatives from selected partnering organisation have the rights and access to move and curate the research data. Data is managed according to relevant national and institutional policies (GDPR (both EU and UK), University of the West of England Information Security¹², and Data management policy by Horizon Europe).

Data generated by the REENGAGE project is available to project partners for dissemination purposes (e.g., research publications, research seminars, etc.). Project partners can access these data through the UWE OneDrive using their user credentials. The Privacy Impact Assessment process provided more insights and helped in making decisions about publishing datasets.

The REENGAGE consortium is devoted to adopting and integrating Open Science practices from the beginning of the project. REENGAGE commits to all mandatory open science practices for all beneficiaries per Grant Agreement (Horizon Europe, Programme Guide, p.38). Anonymised REENGAGE generated data and supporting information will be made open and available as the in-situ component of suitable existing observation repositories (e.g., GEOSS) or cities’ open data portals or other open data initiatives e.g., Zenodo, by employing FAIR principles, allowing for a greater access and availability of qualitative and quantitative in-situ data and better geographical coverage.

Scientific publications will be made available publicly through the research repository Zenodo or through Gold open access journal publications. Where gold open access is not possible, an author version will be accessible through Zenodo or Arxiv repositories. Universities may also make author versions available through their institutional research repositories. For instance, all UWE authored scientific publications are deposited and published through the UWE research repository. All research data necessary to reproduce and to verify the results of the research publications, including the associated metadata, will be made accessible following the FAIR principles in public research data repositories such as Zenodo. The data will be published as soon as possible, but at the latest by the end of the project’s lifetime.

¹² <https://www.uwe.ac.uk/study/it-services/information-security-toolkit/information-security-policies>

11 Data Usage and Processing

In the GREENGAGE project, the collected data is used for different purposes. For example, citizens' inputs are sought to identify general models and solutions to improve and enhance the governance model and to contribute to local administration and public policymaking. NB: Citizens' data is not used to build individual profiles.

Data collected through COs is analysed and -where possible- visualised by technology partners. For example, North Brabant's data is delivered to the DigitTwin and is then integrated so that it can be visualised. Data collected in Apache Druid is used by VISAT, Superset, and the Data Quality Dashboard for visualisation purposes.

Usage and Processing of GREENGAGE datasets is as follows:

For co-creation process data, Collaborative Environment contains a catalogue of ENABLERS, also called INTERLINKERS, which are knowledge and software assets that aids co-creation process. The catalogue success stories of past processes can also be published so these can be reused by other Citizen Observatories as well.

Platform usage and User Statistic data: These statistics are used to measure project level Key Performance Indicators (KPIs).

Use of **Mission data** is as follow:

Anonymised street-view imagery is utilised to extract data related to build environment features and anonymised information on human presence in public spaces through advanced artificial intelligence algorithms on image processing.

Data extracted from street-level imagery is used to derive aggregated metrics and KPIs on the following areas:

- Built Environment Analytics: metrics and KPI to assess the physical characteristics of the urban environment in a particular area (number of buildings, building height, land use types, number and distribution of public amenities, condition of public streets and sidewalks, street furniture).
- Foot traffic analytics: metrics and KPI that provide insight into pedestrian activity levels in different parts of a city (pedestrian volume and density over time) and demographic composition of users (ages and genders) in a particular area or with reference to specific categories of public spaces (i.e., parks, streets, squares)
- Green space analytics: metrics and KPI on the amount of vegetation cover in a particular area in terms of the ratio of green spaces to built-up areas, number of trees and their distribution, and the diversity of plant species.
- Graffiti and vandalism analytics: metrics and KPI on location, frequency and distribution of graffiti and vandalism acts.
- Waste management analytics: metrics and KPI on waste management practices detecting and mapping instances of littering and illegal dumping.
- Parking occupancy analytics: metrics and KPI on parking availability, occupancy rates, and usage patterns.
- Road conditions: metrics on potholes, road surface, safety and hazards

Metrics and KPI are used as is by Pilot cities, as well as for further analytics and integration with complementary tools/data provided by other technology providers. There is no restriction on reuse of aggregated and processed KPI and metrics made available through the designated GREEN Engine platform (applicable licence: CC BY-SA 4.0)

Street quality observations (by GREENGAGE app): This app enables the collection of qualitative and quantitative contextual data from citizens about various Points of Interest within an Observatory. This data can be gathered through surveys or by responding to predefined questions. Through a set of additional task types, citizens can collect various other information – even custom data input. Additionally, the app empowers citizens to contribute by adding specific locations, so called Spots, to a map using their GPS coordinates, allowing them to report observations such as waste, noise, air quality

readings, obstacles, or other environmental or social concerns. Moreover, the app provides citizens with the option to track their movements, with an advanced tracking-analysis software called “MODE” (provided by AIT) to reach a designated POI and “check-in” to complete predefined tasks. This feature not only facilitates engagement but also encourages active participation in monitoring and improving their environment. By combining citizen insights with location-based data, the app serves as a powerful tool for creating a more interactive, informed, and responsive observatory ecosystem. Through the app API, other tools and applications can be integrated into the qualitative collection process as well as to perform further data analysis.

Air quality community observations (such as by Atmotube): This includes citizen-led ambient air quality monitoring using mobile/wearable sensors designed to measure specific pollutants such as PM10, PM2.5, PM1.0, VOCs, as well as environmental parameters like temperature, humidity, and barometric pressure. The purpose of deploying mobile air quality sensors is multifaceted:

1. **Filling Gaps in Coverage:** Mobile sensors enable data collection in areas where official monitoring stations are absent, ensuring a more comprehensive picture of air quality across diverse locations.
2. **Raising Public Awareness:** Engaging citizens in the monitoring process fosters awareness about their local environment and air quality, empowering them to make informed decisions and advocate for change.
3. **Enhancing Data Granularity:** Mobile sensors provide high-resolution air quality data from streets, neighbourhoods, and places that may be far from fixed monitoring stations, offering a richer dataset for localised analysis and decision-making.

By integrating citizen-collected data with official measurements, this initiative strengthens air quality assessments and helps identify specific pollution hotspots while promoting community involvement in environmental stewardship.

The **secondary** research data from open data repositories such as Copernicus (European remote sensing data), UK EDINA DigiMap, Governmental open data portals, Eurostat, research publications from scientific repositories and related white papers are used for research analysis and reporting purposes.

12 Data Preservation, Archiving, and Disposal

Fully anonymised research data will be made openly available through public data repositories, such as Zenodo, GEOSS or the cities' open data portal, MyData¹³, for a wider impact and long term storage.

After completion of the GREENGAGE project (December 2025) personal data will be retained for as long as necessary to provide evidence of compliance with good scientific practice in accordance with the relevant guidelines. Research data must currently be retained for a period of ten years in principle. If this period changes in the future personal data will be stored for a correspondingly shorter or longer period.

North Brabant Pilot has the following policy for data preservation and archiving: The data sets will be stored for **10 years after the research has been completed**. When the project has been finalised, the PPC-officer or RDM-support (library) will be contacted to archive (and publish) the research data in a data Repository. Only the previously designated supervisor and his/her substitute will have access. The BUAS Research Drive creates **disaster recovery back-ups every 24 hours**, to ensure continued availability of the data.

¹³ <https://www.mydata.org/>

13 Ethical and Legal Compliance

UWE was responsible for submitting one main ethics application to UWE's Ethics Committee, but the data collection method was inquired from each partner. Two of the participating partners (University of DEUSTO and BUAS) have their own internal ethics committee that handle their ethics approvals. AIT also vetted data privacy and protection procedures by the Data Protection Officer. More details are covered in D1.9 and D1.10.

To enable participation in the GREENGAGE project, formal consent was sought from all participants prior to taking part in the study. Participants were also reassured of their freedom to withdraw from the project. However, the withdrawal of consent does not affect the lawfulness of processing based on the consent before its withdrawal. Participants information sheets and consent forms were shared before they participated in COs. In general, all user involvement activities were on a voluntary basis and the users received appropriate information on the processing of their personal data and all other ethical implications during the piloting.

Participants were informed of all relevant aspects of the Pilot that might reasonably be expected to influence their decision to participate. Furthermore, informed written/accepted consent by the participants was and is a requirement for their participation in the GREENGAGE project tasks. Volunteers were informed of at least the following:

- Purpose and expected duration of the study.
- Potential risks (if any) and benefits of participating in the study.
- Which data will be collected in the study, in particular, the data directly related to the volunteer and to what degree (and how) confidentiality of such data will be ensured.
- Who will oversee storing the collected data and who will have access to it.
- What kind of processing will be performed with the collected data and for how long the collected data will be maintained.
- Contact persons for the study who can answer any questions the participant may have.

Those who do not wish to give their consent are not included in any studies and resulting publications. A proper procedure is defined and is accessible to participants if they wish to withdraw from the study. Participants can withdraw their consent from GREENGAGE by unticking the consent form acceptance checkbox in the site <https://me.greengage-project.eu/>, which collects profile data for those partaking in GREENGAGE's thematic co-explorations. As a result, participants can no longer log into the GREEN Engine tools. A withdrawal request issued through privacy@greengage-project.eu is met within one month (with extensions for some cases). Also, in the consent form it is mentioned that participants can withdraw from the study by following this set procedure. The partner responsible for the data collection ensures that all instances of the records are removed. However, it is not possible to withdraw and delete data where anonymised data is collected, or data has been summarised prior receiving withdrawal request. This is clearly indicated in the consent form.

14 Data Register

As part of the DOA, a data register is maintained throughout the project, an example is shown in Figure 7. The purpose of the data register is to track:

- What data is collected and for what purposes?
- Who is responsible for the data?
- How long will the data be retained?
- Where will this data be used?
- When was the data collected?
- Where is the data stored?
- Is this data collection compliant to ethics approvals?

All project partners have access to this data register. Study owners and/or data controllers are responsible to maintain up to date data records in the data register.

Email	anonymous
Name	
Last modified time	
Dataset Code	
Please enter the Dataset Name (This field collects the name of the dataset)	Mindmap
Please enter the Dataset Description (this field requires details of what data that is being collected)	The mindmaps were created as part of Redfield Educate Together Primary School's Citizen Observatory workshops. They were focussed on perception of and impacts on safety and threat levels in the local area.
Please enter the Dataset Usage (this field requires you to state that how the collected data will be used in GREENGAGE project and/or after the project)	This data will be used as citizen observations
Please enter Dataset Owner (This field requires you to select the name of pilot/partner who has collected the data)	
Please state when the dataset is effective from i.e., from which date/month the dataset is valid from?	
Please state until when the dataset is effective i.e., until when the data will be managed? (it could be during any time period in the project, throughout the project, or even after the project)	02/06/2025
Please enter the Starting Date of Data Collection (i.e., date on which data was being collected or you started to collect data)	20/05/2024
Is data collection compliant to GREENGAGE Ethics Procedures?	Yes
Please enter the Access Control List i.e., who can access the collected data?	All Greengage team and all EBLN project team within BCC
Please enter the Dataset Version Number (This field helps to link to previously collected data)	1
Please enter the Version Description (*If it is first version, you do not need to fill this field)	
Upload File	
Please Select the Data type (This field collects the type of data that is being managed)	Workshop
Please enter the Dataset Owner (This field requires you to select the name of partner who has collected the data)	Bristol City Council
Please enter the Dataset Description (this field requires details of what data that is being collected)2	
Is data password protected?	No
What is the current status of dataset?	[Collected]: Data has been collected/not-collected;[Anonymised]: Data has been anonymised and personal identifiers have been destroyed;
Where exactly is this dataset stored?	Online
Please provide List of repositories or/and partners who have a copy of this dataset	All Greengage team
Select the Pilot for which this data is related to.	Bristol City Council

Figure 7: Data register example

15 Lessons Learned and Recommendations

Given the large number of project partners, defining a Data Management Plan for the REENGAGE project was not without challenges. For the REENGAGE DMP, it was important to understand the data management procedures and practices of all the partners; this was required to define the project-level DMP later in the project. In REENGAGE, project partners are handling different types of data and therefore, it was important to define procedures how individual partners feed data into the overall project, following project-level guidelines. Considering this, the first version of the DMP was presented from the perspective of individual partners. However, the downside of not defining the DMP at project-level is that it lacks the overall view of what is happening at the project-level and what procedures and practices are being followed in the project. But, as the project progressed and ideas were further developed, the data management plan was revised and articulated at the project-level. Given the challenges that the project faced, following are some recommendations.

Early Defining of Data Management Procedures and Practices

In a complex project like REENGAGE, it is important to start the DMP early and involve all partners from the beginning. Though, at the start of the project, it is important to understand and have knowledge of data management practices of individual partners, this information should be used to define project-level practices at the very start of the project by incorporating individual partners' needs and requirements (where needed) for their data management. This will provide guidelines for all the partners from the start of the project and helps in refining and redefining the practices as the project progresses.

Facilitate Communication among Partners

From the start of the project many meetings were held to define REENGAGE's DMP. But as the project ideas were developing, the project-wide DMP could not be established. What could have been done differently was establishing general guidelines and data flows. For example, later in the project we used a Miro board where we presented the project-wide data flow which gave an overall idea to all the partners what was happening in the project. This helped to revise the DMP and define it at the project-level. In addition to meetings, tools such as Miro board should be used from the start of project to develop ideas and have project-wide view. Early agreement among partners on data management approaches is essential for a smooth collaboration.

Data Sources and Data Register

All data sources should be identified and documented. The purpose of each dataset must be clearly defined and explaining why it is needed and how it will be used. Transparency regarding the origins and accuracy of data is essential for reliability and can be ensured by maintaining a comprehensive data register that tracks sources and updates. Participatory data, such as that from workshops or surveys, should be validated by triangulating with other datasets to ensure their quality and relevance.

Early Definition of Roles and Responsibilities

GDPR Article 26 and 28 requires clear articulation of roles and responsibilities of controllers, joint controllers, and processors of data. It is important to identify controllers/joint controllers, processors, and users at a very early stage of the project to ensure accountability throughout all stages of data management. Clear responsibilities in accordance with GDPR should be defined.

Handling of Personal Data

In a Citizen Science project, involvement of citizens entails collection of personal data, especially to assess inclusive participation from different groups. Assessment of personal data as per relevant regulations must be done before collection and handling of this personal data. Protocols must be implemented to handle sensitive or personal data, ensuring adherence to legal and ethical standards.

Data Organisation and Documentation

Data organisation must be clearly defined, specifying whether it will occur at the project level or if this needs to be handled at the individual partner level. For partner-level organisation, project-level guidelines must be established to ensure seamless integration into the overall data structure. Structured

systems should be implemented to facilitate organised documentation, ensuring data is accessible and traceable.

References

All references are in the footnotes.

AWAITING VALIDATION BY THE EUROPEAN COMMISSION

Appendix

Data Management Plan Questionnaire - City Partners

We hope that you have reviewed the Ethics application prepared by UWE and BUAS (for PNB). This questionnaire has been created to understand Data Management Plan of city partners and their piloting teams. This questionnaire intends to collect details regarding management of data, mainly interviews, questionnaires, walks, surveys, and workshops during piloting phase. These details will be reported in the 1st version of the Data Management Plan (DMP) that is due in Month 6 (June 2023).

General assumption: It is assumed that no personal data will be collected, and only anonymous data will be stored/shared with partners as per the ethical approval (refer to ethics application).

Tools (e.g., Qualtrics, EU Survey, or GREENGAGE tools used by city partners) planned to be used and resulting data will be covered in the 2nd version of the Data Management Plan deliverable that is due in M30, therefore, this information is not required in this questionnaire.

There is a separate questionnaire that has been sent to technology partners and it aims to gather information about data management through GREENGAGE toolbox.

General Information

1. City Partner Name:

Following Sections intend to collect information on how the data will be collected and managed by City partners throughout the project life cycle.

1. Data Collection

Please provide the following details regarding data collection

- i. What type of citizen data will be collected and what are the data attributes? [e.g., age group, experience etc]
- ii. What method(s) will be used for data collection [e.g., online survey text-based, paper-based postal survey, interview i.e., audio/video recording or manual notes taking, walks i.e., observations etc.].
- iii. What data formats will be used? [e.g., digital format and file type, hand-written, audio file, video file, etc.]
- iv. How would you ensure data quality?
- v. How the data will be used?
- vi. Are there any restrictions on data reuse?
- vii. Is there any personal/confidential data being collected. If yes, how will you handle the confidential data?

viii. How will you share the anonymous data with GREENGAGE partners for analysis, reporting and publication purposes?

2. Data organization and documentation

Please provide a detailed description on how data will be organized and documented, including the naming conventions, file formats, and metadata standards that will be used.

3. Data storage and backup

In the consortium Ethics application, we are claiming that anonymised data will be stored on UWE OneDrive and access will be restricted to partners. If you plan to store the above data on different repositories, then please provide details:

i. Where and how the data will be stored during the project and after it is completed. Please include information about the type of storage media that will be used, the location of the data, etc.

ii. How backup measures (including backup frequency) will be implemented? Who will be responsible for data backup?

iii. Please provide a description of how you will ensure security and preservation of data including any requirements for data encryption or access control.

4. Data sharing and access

i. Please provide details on how data will be shared (such as through data repositories or archives), including any restrictions or limitations on access, and any procedures for obtaining data access.

ii. As per the consortium ethics application, such data will be stored/kept on UWE OneDrive. How will you share the data with UWE and what security measures will be needed for storing, sharing, and accessing the data?

5. Data preservation and archiving

i. Will data be preserved and archived after the completion of the project, if so, how?

ii. Is there any data disposal plan? If yes, then at what stage of the project the data will be disposed?

6. Roles and responsibilities

Can you please identify roles and responsibilities of data being managed? Possible roles are i) Data producers: Providers of existing or new raw data ii) Data consumers: Users of existing or new (processed) data iii) Data custodians/curators: Responsible for taking care of (or protecting) the data lifecycle i.e., from collection to processing, storage, security and sharing.

7. Ethical and legal considerations

Please also refer to the Consortium Ethics application where consent form and participant information sheets are prepared. Please let us know if any ethical or legal considerations associated with the collection, storage, and sharing of the data, including any requirements for informed consent, data privacy, or confidentiality is missing? Are there any legal, ethical reasons obstructing to open access to data?

Note:

As part of DOA, a data register will be maintained throughout the project. The purpose of the data register will be to track: What data is collected and for what purposes? Who is responsible for the data? how long the data will be retained? Where will this data be used? When was the data collected? Where is data stored? Is this data collection compliant to Ethics approval? UWE will share the data register link soon.

Data Management Plan Questionnaire - Technology Partners

We hope that you have also reviewed the Ethics application that is being submitted for scrutiny. The application identifies abstract level data collection and how will it be stored on UWE OneDrive.

This questionnaire has been created to collect information for Data Management Plan deliverable that is due in Month 6. The aim is to capture data management details for piloting data that will be collected through the GEENGAGE Technological tools. Therefore, this questionnaire is being sent to technology partners for information gathering. We understand that as part of T2.6 and WP4, Workflows and Data flows are being defined based on the Pilot specifications. So, this is ideal time to capture data management for the project.

*As description of tool has already been covered in Deliverable 4.1, so details regarding the tool is not required. If there are additional data related details, then please include in this survey. The following Sections intend to collect information on how the data will be managed by Technology partners throughout the project life cycle.

General Information

1. Partner Name:
2. Tool Name:

REENGAGE Technology Tools specific Questions:

1. Data Collection

Please provide the following details regarding data collection

- i. What are the types of Data being collected?
- ii. What is the method(s) used for data collection?
- iii. What data formats will be used? [e.g., digital format and file type, audio file, video file, etc.]
- iv. How would you ensure data quality?
- v. Can you please identify level of confidentiality that will be applied including Strictly confidential, currently confidential but public at a later stage, or public.
- vi. Any existing data being used? Does new collected data will complement existing data?
- vii. How will the data be used?
- viii. Any restrictions on data reuse?

ix. As mentioned in the Ethics application, we assume no personal/confidential data will be collected. Is this correct assumption. If private/confidential/personal data is collected then how will it be protected, anonymised etc., before sharing with others.

2. Data organization and documentation

Please provide a detailed description on how data will be organized and documented, including the naming conventions, file formats, and metadata standards that will be used.

3. Data storage and backup

i. Where and how the data will be stored during the project and after it is completed. Please include information about the type of storage media that will be used, the location of the data etc.

ii. How backup measures (including backup frequency) that will be implemented? Who will be responsible for data backup?

iii. Please provide a description of how you will ensure security and preservation of data including any requirements for data encryption or access control.

4. Data sharing and access

i. Please provide details on how data will be shared, including any restrictions or limitations on access, and any procedures for obtaining data access. Please provide information about how the data will be shared, such as through data repositories or archives.

ii. As per Consortium Agreement, Data will be stored/kept on UWE OneDrive. How will you share the data with UWE and what security measures will be applied for storing, sharing, and accessing the data? Which data will be shared?

5. Data preservation and archiving

i. Will data be preserved and archived after the completion of the project, if so, how?

ii. Is there any data disposal plan? If yes, then at what stage of the project the data will be disposed?

6. Roles and responsibilities

Can you please identify roles and responsibilities of data being managed? Possible roles are i) Data producers: Providers of existing or new raw data ii) Data consumers: Users of existing or new (processed) data iii) Data custodians/curators: Responsible for taking care of (or protecting) the data lifecycle i.e., from collection to processing, storage, security and sharing.

7. Ethical and legal considerations

Please also refer to the Consortium Ethics application where consent form and participant information sheets are prepared. Please let us know if any ethical or legal considerations associated with the collection, storage, and sharing of the data, including any requirements for informed consent, data privacy, or confidentiality is missing? Are there any legal, ethical reasons obstructing to open access to data?

GREENGAGE Pilot specific data management Questions:

1. What data will be passed on to other tools for further processing?
2. How raw and processed data will be shared and managed?

Note:

As part of DOA, a data register will be maintained throughout the project. The purpose of the data register will be to track: What data is collected and for what purposes? Who is responsible for the data? how long the data will be retained? Where will this data be used? When was the data collected? Where is data stored? Is this data collection compliant to Ethics approval?